

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Reaction of rice varieties to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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We evaluated 28 rices for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) in the field and in a glasshouse in 1983 kharif. The rices were received through the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. In the field, WBPH populations were recorded 50 and 60 d after transplanting (DT). Mean population was 3.7 to 19.2/hill at 50 DT and 2.6 to 23.9/hill at 60 DT. Populations declined between 50 and 60 DT on all rices except RP2149-88, RP2147-73, and TN1 (see table).

When evaluated in the seedling bulk test, only eight rices were resistant to WBPH (see table). Cultures with Velutha Cheera as parent were resistant and had low WBPH populations in the field. Cultures with Andrewsali, IET6288, Manoharsali, or Ptb 33 as parents were susceptible.

It is interesting to note that IET6288 and Ptb 33 are resistant to WBPH. IET6288 received resistance from Ptb 21 through CR55-35/IR8. Their high degree of resistance may have been lost in the crossing program. Some rices with susceptible reaction in the seedling bulk test had field resistance to WBPH. The nature of resistance of these rices is being further evaluated. ♪

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Reaction of some promising rice cultures and cultivars to WBPH in the field and in a glasshouse, Pantnagar, India.

Designation	Donor or cross	WBPH (av no./hill)		Damage rating ^a	Reaction ^b
		50 DT	60 DT		
Anaikomban	Donor	4.1	6.8	1.4	R
Eswarmanglam	Donor	5.0	5.9	1.5	R
Mudu Kiriya	Donor	7.7	3.2	2.0	R
Rathu Heenati	Donor	10.4	4.0	2.1	R
MO I	Donor	4.9	6.2	2.2	R
RP2068-17-2-1	Swarndhan/Velutha Cheera	3.7	3.2	2.6	R
RP2068-17-2-2	Swarndhan/Velutha Cheera	4.1	2.8	2.7	R
Ptb33	Donor	6.4	4.4	3.0	R
RP2068-18-4-2	Swarndhan/Velutha Cheera	5.1	4.8	3.6	MR
RP2095-123-1-1	Vikram/Andrewsali	6.2	9.2	5.5	S
RP2095-123-1-5	Vikram/Andrewsali	10.1	4.6	6.1	S
ARC5956	Donor	6.5	4.1	6.8	S
IET7575	Sona/Manoharsali	11.3	9.9	6.8	S
ARC7080	Donor	10.6	7.6	7.4	HS
ARC5984	Donor	3.5	4.5	7.5	HS
Leb Mue Nahng	Donor	6.6	2.6	7.5	HS
IET7948	Ptb 33/TN1	1.2	6.8	7.6	HS
ARC6619	Donor	6.6	7.1	7.9	HS
Andrewsali	Donor	8.1	5.4	7.9	HS
RP2149-109	IET6288/Phalguna	16.4	13.7	8.2	HS
RP2149-71	IET6288/Phalguna	6.2	6.7	8.5	HS
RP2149-73	IET6288/Phalguna	9.3	17.7	8.6	HS
RP2149-88	IET6288/Phalguna	6.8	11.9	8.7	HS
RP2149-58	IET6288/Phalguna	8.1	5.7	8.7	HS
ARC10572 A	Donor	9.3	9.4	8.7	HS
RP2149-96	IET6288/Phalguna	8.7	9.5	9.0	HS
RP2149-86	IET6288/Phalguna	10.0	8.0	9.0	HS
ARC10550	Donor	19.7	17.7	9.0	HS
TN1	—	15.9	23.9	9.0	HS

^a Based on Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Response of different rices to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) populations from different locations in Indonesia

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horváth) is widely distributed in Indonesia.

Infestations are generally low, but large populations can cause serious damage.

In 1984 dry season, we collected WBPH from Muara Lawai, South Sumatra; Bulu Kumba, South Sulawesi; Munggu, Bali; and Mataram, Lombok. We

Table 1. Resistance of rice varieties to 5 WBPH populations in the greenhouse, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Resistance ^a on indicated variety				
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	IR36	Colombo
Muara Lawai	8.3	5	3	4	4.3
Bulu Kumba	8.3	3	3	5	2.3
Munggu	7	3	5	5	3.0
Mataram	8.3	4.3	5	5	2.3
Greenhouse	9	3.1	5	—	1.7

^a On scale of 0-9: 0 = no damage, 9 = all plants dead.